

The IT theorem and dimensional analysis

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0. The TT theorem (Barenblatt 96)

Let $x = (x_1, \dots, x_k)$, $y = (y_1, \dots, y_m)$ and z be (tuples of) physical quantities such that $x_1, \dots, x_k$ are dimensionally independent and the dimensions of $y_1, \dots, y_m$ and z are linear combinations of the dimensions of $x_1, \dots, x_k$:

$$dz = dx \cdot P = \sum_{j=1}^k dx_j \cdot P_j$$

$$dy_i = dx \cdot Q_i = \sum_{j=1}^k dx_j \cdot Q_{ij}$$

Let z be related to x and y by a function f that fulfills the covariance principle of physics

$$z = f(x, y) \quad \wedge \quad f \text{ covariant}$$

Then f can be written as

$$f(x, y) = \prod x^p * \varphi(\pi_1, \dots, \pi_m) \text{ where}$$

$$\pi_i = y_i / \prod x^{q_i}$$

(0)

- What are "physical quantities"?
- What does it mean for such quantities to be "dimensionally independent"?
- What does it mean for a function to fulfill the "covariance principle"?
- How can such principle be formulated?
- What are applications of the Π Theorem?
- What are its applications?

1. The standard example (flow in a pipe, Reynolds n.)

$$\frac{dp}{dx} = f(\rho, \nu, d, \mu)$$

↓ Π

$$\frac{dp}{dx} \frac{\rho \nu^2}{d}$$

$$= \frac{\rho \nu^2}{d} \varphi\left(\frac{\rho \nu d}{\mu}\right)$$

Reynolds, 1883!

2. Physical quantities (variables)

These are "quantities that can be measured" in a finite system of units:

$$\mu: Q \rightarrow U_n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

The idea is that $\mu x u$ denotes the measure (magnitude, value...) of the quantity x in units u .

3. Covariance principle (reality of measurements)

$$\forall x: Q, u, v: U_n, \lambda: \Lambda = \mathbb{R}_+^n$$

$$\frac{\mu x \lambda * u}{\mu x u} = \frac{\mu x \lambda * v}{\mu x v} \quad (1)$$

In other words $\mu x \lambda * u \mid \mu x u$ does not depend on u !

4. Dimension function, dimensions

From (1) it follows that the dimension function

$$\Phi: \mathcal{Q} \rightarrow \Lambda \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

$$\Phi x \lambda = \mu x \lambda * u \mid \mu x u$$

satisfies

$$\Phi x (\lambda_1 \mid \lambda_2) = \Phi x \lambda_1 \mid \Phi x \lambda_2 \quad \forall x: \mathcal{Q}, \lambda_1, \lambda_2: \Lambda$$

□ (by equational reasoning) (2)

$$\Phi x \lambda_1 \mid \Phi x \lambda_2$$

$$= \{ \text{by def. of } \Phi, u \text{ arbitrary} \}$$

$$\mu x \lambda_1 * u \mid \mu x \lambda_2 * u$$

$$= \{ \text{by setting } v = \lambda_2 * u \}$$

$$\mu x \lambda_1 * \frac{1}{\lambda_2} * v \mid \mu x v$$

$$= \{ \text{by def of } \Phi \}$$

$$\Phi x (\lambda_1 / \lambda_2) \quad \square$$

The function $\Phi x : \Lambda \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is called the **dimension function of x** and denoted by $[x]$:

$$[x] = \Phi x : \Lambda \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

From (2) it follows (Barendt 96, section 1.1.4) that $[x]$ is a power-law monomial

$$[x] (\lambda_1 \dots \lambda_n) = \lambda_1^{d_1 x} * \dots * \lambda_n^{d_n x} \quad (3)$$

with $d_1, \dots, d_n : \mathbb{Q} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ (in fact $\mathbb{Q} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$).

The numbers $d_1 x, \dots, d_n x$ are called the dimensions of the space x . The numbers dz, dx_j and dy_j in

$$dz = dx \cdot p = \sum_{j=1}^k dx_j \cdot p_j$$

$$dy_i = dx \cdot q_i = \sum_{j=1}^k dx_j \cdot q_{i,j}$$

The premises of the IT Theorem are the values of d

$$d : \mathcal{Q} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n \quad (4)$$

$$dx = (d_1 x, \dots, d_n x)$$

for the quantities z, x_j, y_i (with some abuse of notation for dx). Notice that by (3) and (4)

$$d(x \cdot y) = dx + dy$$

5. Dimensionless quantities

A quantity x : Q is dimensionless $\equiv dx = 0$.

From (3) and from the definition of $\mathbb{E}$ it follows

$$x \text{ dimensionless} \equiv \mu x \lambda * u = \mu x u$$

$\forall \lambda: \Lambda, u: U_n$: The value of dimensionless quantities is the same in any system of units.

6. Dimensional independence

The quantities $x_1, \dots, x_k$ are dimensionally indep.

$\equiv$

$dx_1, \dots, dx_k: \mathbb{R}^k$ are linearly independent.

Let $x_1, \dots, x_k$ be dim. indep. Then, $\forall u: U_n$,

$A: \mathbb{R}^n, \exists \lambda: \Lambda$ such that

$$\mu x_i, \lambda * u = A * \mu x_i, u \quad (5)$$

$$\mu x_j, \lambda * u = \mu x_j, u \quad j = 2, \dots, k$$

□ L.A., Borenbblatt 86, section 1.1.5. The basic idea is that

(5)

$$\equiv \int x_i, \lambda = A \equiv \lambda_1 * \dots * \lambda_n \quad \frac{d_n x_i}{\lambda_n} = A$$

$$\int x_j, \lambda = 1 \equiv \lambda_1^{d_1} x_j^{d_j} * \dots * \lambda_n^{d_n} x_j^{d_j} = 1$$

Then take logarithms and apply the def. of dimensional independence ...

□ 9

7. The Π Theorem revisited

The idea of the proof is: start from

$$z = f(x, y) \quad (6)$$

with the assumptions about x, y and z

$$dz = dx \cdot P = \sum_{j=1}^k dx_j \cdot P_j \quad (7)$$

$$dy_i = dx \cdot Q_i = \sum_{j=1}^k dx_j \cdot Q_{ij} \quad (8)$$

First, define

$$\Pi = z / \prod x_j^P = z / \prod_{j=1}^k x_j^{P_j} \quad (9)$$

Then, with $\Pi, \dots, \Pi_m$ defined as in (9):

$$\pi_i = y_i / \prod x^{q_i} \quad (i = 1, \dots, m)$$

and by definition of z and π we have

$$\pi = \frac{1}{\prod x^p} f(x, \pi_1 * \prod x^{q_1}, \dots, \pi_m * \prod x^{q_m})$$

What is

$$\pi = g(x, \pi_1, \dots, \pi_m)$$

The next, crucial step is to argue that g cannot depend on x . The reasoning is by contradiction. First, notice that $\pi, \pi_1, \dots, \pi_m$ are dimensionless by (7) and (8). Then, notice that, because of (5) one can find a system of units $\lambda * u$

(for any u !) such that

$$\mu x_1 \lambda * u = A * \mu x_1 u$$

$$\mu x_j \lambda * u = \mu x_j u \quad j = 2 \dots k$$

Because the measures of $\pi_1, \pi_2, \dots, \pi_m$ would not change in the new units, g must be independent of x_1 . The argument is identical for $x_2 \dots x_k$. Hence g is independent of x :

$$g(x_1, \pi_1, \dots, \pi_m) = \varphi(\pi_1, \dots, \pi_m)$$

Therefore

$$z = \pi * \prod x^p = \prod x^p * \varphi(\pi_1, \dots, \pi_m)$$

as stated in (0).

The proof sketch raises two obvious questions:

- Can we turn the sketch in a formal proof?
- What would be the role of the hypothesis " f covariant" in a formal proof?

The key for answering these questions is to raise another question:

- What is the type of f ?

This question is crucial because, as it turns out, there are in fact two functions involved in the TT theorem: one that relates the physical quantities x, y, z and one that relates their measures in an arbitrary system of units u !

8. Some references

- Borenblatt 26 Scaling, self-similarity and intermediate asymptotics, G.I. Borenblatt, CUP, 1986
- Bridgman 22 Dimensional Analysis, P. W. Bridgman, Yale Univ. Press, 1922
- Gibbings 11 Dimensional analysis, J. C. Gibbings, Springer, 2011
- Buckingham 1 On physically similar systems, Phys. Rev., 1914
- Buckingham 2 Model experiments and the form of physical equations, Trans. ASME, 1915

- Jonsen Δ Dan Jonsen, The PI Theorem revisited, ArXiv, 2020
- Jonsen Δ Dan Jonsen, Dimensional Analysis: a century update, ArXiv, 2014
- Stewart Δ Theory of dimensions, S. G. Stewart, 2017
- deGourlay The double interpretation of the equations of physics and the quest for common meaning, Standardization in Measurement, Schwandt + Huber Eds., 2015

